

MANAGEMENT OF NADIVRANA [PILONIDAL SINUS] IN AYURVEDA – A CASE STUDY***¹Dr. Indranil Babasaheb Magdum, ²Dr. Turlapati Srinivas Narsimha**¹MS Shalyatantra, Assistant Professor, Dept. of Shalyatantra, Dr. S.P. Patil Ayurvedic Medical College, Kodoli, Kolhapur, MH.²MS Shalyatantra, HOD & Professor, Dept. of Shalyatantra, Dr. S.P. Patil Ayurvedic Medical College, Kodoli, Kolhapur, MH.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Indranil Babasaheb Magdum**MS Shalyatantra, Assistant Professor, Dept. of Shalyatantra, Dr. S.P. Patil Ayurvedic Medical College, Kodoli, Kolhapur, MH. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19434952>**How to cite this Article:** ¹Dr. Indranil Babasaheb Magdum, ²Dr. Turlapati Srinivas Narsimha (2026). Management Of Nadvirana [Pilonidal Sinus] In Ayurveda – A Case Study. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 12(4), 403–405.

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ABSTRACT

Nadi Vrana is a common disorder in tropics due to unhygienic conditions. Clinically *Nadi Vrana* forms if abscess is avoid or treated improperly and ineffectively with post-operative complications and complaints of recurrences in most of the cases by the line of treatment adopted by modern surgeons. In spite of tremendous progress in the field of modern surgery, still there or greatly analyzed chances of recurrence are noticed. *Nadi Vrana* occurs in different sites of body due to different pathogens. So a medicine which acts systemically is also required for the management of *Nadi Vrana*. Hence para-surgical procedure planned which ultimately fulfills all the lacunas or pitfalls encountered in the present day management. Hence the proper, effective, simple, safe, non-emulative and non-invasive procedure i.e. *Varti* application is advised because it is not only on innovative technique but also devoid of any complication or recurrence.

KEYWORDS: *Nadivirana*, Pilonidal sinus, *Varti*.**INTRODUCTION**

The term *Ayurveda* means the science of life. It is traditionally considered as *Upveda* of *Atharva Veda*^[1] & has been categorized into *Astangas*.^[2] Among the eight categories of *Ayurveda Shalya Tantra* one of the predominant branches lays emphasis. Diagnosis of wounds, extraction of foreign bodies and description of instruments are dealt in depth in *Shalya Tantra*^[3] only.

The word *Vrana* means to break or tearing of the body. The word is derived from the verbal root of '*Vrana*' It means anything that causing discontinuity of the skin and flesh of the effected part. When a surgeon opens an *Apakwa* swelling (*Vrana Shopha*), and ignores a *Pakwa Vrana Shopha* out a negligence or ignorance and if the patient continues unhealthy food and activities, then the pus break down the unimpaired intact tissues, passes deeper and deeper destroying the *Vrana Sthana*, because of its moving inside greatly it is known as *Gati* and since the spread is through a tube, it is called as *Nadi*.^[4]

Nadi Vrana is an ulcer having a tract extending into in the deeper tissues. *Nadi Vrana* is associated with presence of the large number of recesses or cavity in an ulcer. When excessive infiltration of pus burrows deeply then it can be called as *Gati*. Thus, *Gati* is synonym of *Nadi Vrana*.^[5]

Nadi Vrana is comprised and treated as a Sinus. A Sinus is defined as a blind tract leading from surface down into the tissue and lines either by granulation tissue or by epithelium tissue. It persists due to the presence of in depth foreign body (sequestrum, suturing material etc.) non dependent drainage and infection.^[6]

In our *Ayurveda*, *Acharyas* have explained in detail about the management of *Nadi Vrana* with different treatment modalities. *Varti* application is one among them which does not require anaesthesia and having good curative properties with wrathful results. The *Varti* is considered to possess an anti-inflammatory and good broad spectrum activity. It must be remembered that *Nadi Vrana* is a chronic non-healing ulcer (*Dushta Vrana*) and

may occurs due to specific organism also. *Acharya Chakradatta* explained *Ghonta Phaladi Varti* which have *Shodhana* and *Ropana* properties, thus selected for the study and help in treating the *Nadi Vrana* effectively.^[7]

AIM & OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Aim – Management of *Nadivrana* [Pilonidal sinus] in *Ayurveda*.

OBJECTIVES

To study the role of *Ghonta Phaladi Varti* in the management of *Nadivrana* w.s.r. to Pilonidal sinus.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

CASE STUDY

The case study was conducted on male patient having age of 35 years which comes to OPD of *Shalyatantra* department in our hospital with presenting complaints of *Ruja* [pain,] *Sparshaasahatva* [Tenderness], *Kandu* [Itching] and *Daha* [Burning sensation] since from 5-6 months.

History of present illness

Patient was asymptomatic before 5-6 months, then he develops pain, tenderness, itching, burning sensation. This all complaints, discomfort make patients daily activities and life difficult. So, patient comes to OPD for further management.

Past history – H/O – Constipation [on & off]

Family history – No H/O any illness

Personal history – Excessive consumption of Non-vegetarian diet, Street food consumption, Normal sleep, Work in seating position, No addiction.

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

The effect of *Ghonta Phaladi Varti* in the management of *Nadivrana* in 30 days of case study is as follows.

	Symptoms	Before treatment	After treatment
VAS Scale	<i>Ruja</i> [Pain] & <i>Sparshaasahatva</i> [Tenderness]	9	3
Symptom			
	<i>Kandu</i> [Itching]	+++	+
	Mild discharge	++	+
	<i>Daha</i> [Burning sensation]	+++	+

Gradation of symptoms

+ = Mild, ++ = Moderate, +++ = Severe

1 - 3 = Mild, 4 - 6 = Moderate, 7 - 10 = Severe

Nadivrana is in acute case, helps to heal faster, therefore an attempt is made to treat *Nadivrana* with *Ghonta Phaladi Varti* in 30 days of study. It is found effective in this case study.

Ghonta Phala helps in reducing the inflammation and promotes wound healing by its *Vrana Shodaka*, *Vrana Ropaka*, *Krimigna* and *Vatapittahara* properties. *Saindhav Lavanam* reduces discharge and pain by its *Tridoshaghna* properties, *Shoolagna* and *Shophagna* properties, *Lekhana* and *Ropana* properties, helps in healing of ulcers. *Laksha* reduces burning sensation &

General examination

- PR = 78/min
- BP = 120/90 mm of Hg
- Temperature = 98.6⁰ F
- Weight = 70 kg.

Systemic examination

- RS = Clear, AE=BE,
- CNS = Conscious, oriented
- CVS = No murmur, S₁, S₂ Normal
- P/A = Soft, No tenderness

Ashtavidha Parikshana / Examination

- *Nadi* = 78/min
- *Mala* = *Asamyaka*, *Malavshthambha*
- *Mutra* = *Samyaka*
- *Jivha* = *Alpa Sama*
- *Sparsha* = *Shitoshna*
- *Shabda* = *Spashta*
- *Druka* = *Prakruta*
- *Aakruti* = *Madhyam*

Surgery / Treatment history – No any history.

Local examination

- Burning sensation+
- Mild discharge through the opening with or without pain.
- Multiple External openings.

Management

In this case study, management of *Nadivrana* is done by *Ghonta Phaladi Varti*.^[8] *Ghonta Phaladi Varti* was said to be effective in *Nadi Vrana*. It is described in *Chakradatta*, *Nadi Vrana Chikitsa Adhyaya*.

local temperature from its *Sheeta Veerya*, reduces colour of surrounding skin from its *Varna Prasadana* properties. *Pooga Phala* from its *Kaphapittanashaka*, *Krimighna* and *Vrana Ropaka* actions it is useful in treatment of *Nadi Vrana*. *Jyotishmati* having *Kushthaghna* and *Vranaghna* properties. *Snuhi Ksheera* from its *Kaphavatahara*, *Pitta Shodhana* and unique properties like *Shodhana* of *Rasa*, *Rakta*, *Mamsa*, *Meda*, *Majja* is very useful in inflammatory conditions like *Nadi Vrana*. *Arkaksheera* is *Kaphavataashamaka*, having *Sara*, *Krimigna* and *Vishagna* properties useful in treating non healing ulcers like *Nadi Vrana*.

DISCUSSION

Varti is mainly indicated in *Vrana* with minute external opening and in *Antaha Shalyaja Vrana*. These *Vartis* prepared with *Shodhana* and *Ropana Dravyas* does debridement of the slough (or) unhealthy tissue, alleviates all the vitiated Doshas and facilitates for the healing process. Every third day probing sessions are conducted for removing any obstructive pathology in the sinus tract by which adequate drainage could be done and the tract become more suitable for healing in proper way.

Ghonta Phaladi Varti consists of *Ghonta Phala Twaka*, *Saindhav Lavanam*, *Laksha*, *Puga Phala*, *Jyotishmati*, *Snuhi Ksheera* & *Arka Ksheera*. It is all known to possess *Tridosha Shamaka* and anti-inflammatory activities irrespective of the organisms due to its *Teekshna*, *Sookshma*, *Sara*, *Krimighna* and *Vishagna* properties. It acts as local degrading agent and keeps the tract clean and devoid of purulent substances. Its *Laghu*, *Rooksha* and *Sara* properties enable it to penetrate deeper into the tissues and acts against the tendency of body towards formation of fibrous tissues there by resulting in non-healing nature of *Nadi Vrana* besides, after healing scar tissue formation is less.

CONCLUSION

In *Nadivrana* case study, presenting signs & symptoms like *Ruja* [pain,] *Sparshaasahatva* [Tenderness], *Kandu* [Itching] and *Daha* [Burning sensation], mild discharge are markedly reduced in this 30 days of study. In conclusion, *Ghonta Phaladi Varti* is significantly effective in the management of *Nadivrana* with proper follow up of *Pathya* and *Apathya*.

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